

Critical flaw in the LMD system in module compensation: Development of two forms of equation by KPIs for measuring compensation risk probability with algorithms and codes

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Abstract. Universities that implemented the LMD (License, Master, Doctorate) system sought to enhance and standardize curricula, with the goal of increasing students' international recognition. However, student performance in the professional realm has not met anticipated standards. Research has consistently shown that the LMD system has failed to address the issues related to students' professional integration, largely due to skills that often do not align with professional requirements. This study highlights a significant factor contributing to the system's shortcomings: module compensation.

In this work, we introduce the development of two fundamental and user-friendly equations, grounded in key performance indicators, designed to measure the probability of compensation risk. This measurement is considered crucial for assessing the effectiveness of graduation outcomes. We firmly believe that these equations, intended for evaluating compensation risk, will assist professors and academic administrators in making informed decisions, by enabling the review of courses content or adjustments to examinations, these tools can help mitigate module compensation, which this study identifies as a critical flaw within the LMD system. Moreover, algorithms, listings, and programming codes are provided to facilitate the straightforward use of these equations, either through a simple spreadsheet interface or a more advanced IT development setup.

Keywords: Compensation of modules, LMD system, key performance indicators in education, catch-up exams, performance in education

1 Introduction

Following the failure of the LMD (License, Master, Doctorate) system in several countries, particularly in North Africa and other French-speaking regions, researchers have extensively documented the system's ineffectiveness. To address this issue, it is crucial to understand the root causes of its inefficiency. These issues often become apparent not during a student's university studies but in the labor market. The primary criticism of the LMD system stems from a common problem. Despite being implemented over 20 years ago following the Bologna Process, observations have revealed numerous failures; however, literature reviews rarely provide corrective solutions, or such solutions are difficult to find. This study identifies a critical flaw in the LMD system and introduces two equations based on carefully selected key performance indicators (KPIs). These equations are designed to measure the probability of compensation risk, highlighting cases where students might achieve high grades yet possess inadequate skills in their major field.

2 Context of research

2.1 Literature review on the use of KPIs in education

In organizations, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are commonly used to measure various concepts. In higher education institutions (HEIs), KPIs are considered essential for evaluating performance (Budimir, Lutitsky, & Idlbek, 2016). Additionally, dashboards, as a component of Business Intelligence, and their continuous evaluation are employed to enhance the monitoring of KPIs (Yoo, Lee, Jo, & Park, 2015). However, while KPIs define what should be measured and how, whether through direct reading or correlation, their application often focuses on broad criteria such as leadership or general quality, particularly in the context of a performance policy in the UK (Breakwell & Tytherleigh, 2010). This approach tends to be managerial rather than academic.

In simpler terms, the KPIs found in the literature for assessing HEI performance generally address global aspects and rarely focus on students directly. Relevant KPIs identified are often analyzed using methods such as the Analytic Network Process (ANP), which, although effective, is complex (Verdecho, Alfaro-Saiz, Rodríguez-Rodríguez, & al., 2021), or the PESTEL analysis in the same field (Laaziri, Benmoussa, Mouchtachi, & El Amrani, 2024). This work aims to facilitate teachers' engagement with the practice of monitoring student performance through KPIs in a straightforward manner. This approach is intended for educators who may not possess advanced IT or statistical skills.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

The LMD system was introduced after the Bologna Process as a solution to the rigidity of previous educational systems. Several countries adopted it, including

those that participated in the Bologna Process in Europe, as well as North African countries, countries in the Sahel, Turkey, Switzerland, Norway, Russia, and Middle Eastern countries such as Lebanon, Syria, and Jordan.

These countries often adapt the framework to fit their national education policies and regulations. The widespread adoption of the LMD system has facilitated student mobility, recognition of qualifications, and comparability of academic degrees across borders. Moreover, according to Woldegiorgis (2018), the Bologna Process has significantly impacted the regionalization of higher education policies in countries outside Europe, particularly in North Africa, where adjustments to the LMD system were necessary as these countries are not part of the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS).

However, after a few years, it became evident that the system still did not deliver the expected skills. Increasingly, countries are criticizing the system's failure to meet educational standards, especially regarding student skills (Ndjomo, 2020). The system has also faced criticism for the educational practices it imposes (Azzi, 2012), a critique that has persisted over the years and extends to concerns about professional skills and the reliability of diplomas (Nouri, 2020). Recent research has focused on the system's limitations and resistance to unproductivity (Yone-mura, 2020), comparisons between employment and graduation under the LMD system (Laaziri & al., 2023), and teaching practices (El Kirat El Allame, 2020). Additionally, criticisms have addressed the system's implementation, which does not align with the practices of the adopting countries (Teclou, Kpelao, & Saka, 2020).

In the context studied, the observed populations experience a "widespread use of the compensation mechanism established between modules, semesters, and years within the LMD system" (CSEFRS ³ 2018). According to the same source, some academics even describe this compensation as "gifts for students to ensure the success of the LMD reform." Furthermore, module compensation also grants access to catch-up sessions, which faculty administrators pejoratively view as "the right to a catch-up exam without a minimum grade threshold," considering these to be additional forms of the same recourse to compensation.

Despite widespread questioning of the LMD system's adaptation, none of the cited works or other consulted sources address the issue of module compensation.

3 Problem statement

It is important to understand beforehand how these compensations between modules could negatively impact the skills of the students. Indeed, the LMD system does not effectively respond to the requirements for hard skills. In fact, the LMD was not established as it is currently implemented. Additionally, students who attend the catch-up sessions may have a second chance to obtain higher marks than those who have already sealed their modules in the normal session and are therefore no longer allowed to improve their performance.

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To better understand the flaw caused by the compensation principle in the LMD system, it should be noted that the system is based on a modular approach where validation at 10/20 of each module (which includes two or more subjects within the same discipline) is irreversible throughout the curriculum and independent of the final average score. Compensating the modules thus increases the success rate, but in a biased manner.

To illustrate this situation, Table 1 and Table 2 present the case of two students studying in the same program, *Applied Mathematics*, in the sixth semester, who have obtained nearly the same overall average but have different marks in the units.

Module	Type	Unit	Mark (/20)	Average	Difference	Compensation
1	Major	Integration II	12	12	+2	No
2	Major	Topology II	13	14	+3	No
3	Secondary	Partial differential equations	14	14	+4	No
		Nonlinear programming	13			
		Scientific calculation	15			
4	Cultural (soft skills)	Foreign languages	6	5	-5	Yes
		Law civics and citizenship	4			
Total semester average				11.00		

Table 1. Marks and average of student 1

Module	Type	Unit	Mark (/20)	Average	Difference	Compensation
1	Major	Integration II	7	7	-3	Yes
2	Major	Topology II	8	8	-2	Yes
3	Secondary	Partial differential equations	13	9.75	-0.25	Yes
		Nonlinear programming	8			
		Scientific calculation	8.25			
4	Cultural (soft skills)	Foreign languages	19	19.5	+9.5	No
		Law civics and citizenship	20			
Total semester average				11.06		

Table 2. Marks and average of student 2

We note that :

- Student 1 achieved satisfactory results in both major and secondary modules (hard skills), with only one compensation for the soft skills' module.
- Student 2 recorded insufficient results in both major and secondary modules (hard skills), but were all compensated by the excess points coming from the soft skills' module.

In the end, both students obtained the same average for the semester. However, the first student can be considered competent in mathematics due to their performance in the major modules, while the second student, despite being considered mediocre in mathematics, aligns with the first due to the compensations.

Based on the fact that module compensation alters the effectiveness of graduations, specifically major modules, it becomes obvious to ask the following questions.

- *How can we determine if a student is potentially exposed to possible compensation?*
- *How can we calculate the probability that a student will compensate for modules?*

Addressing these two questions leads to the definition of two key performance indicators. These indicators form the basis of equations that measure the probability of compensation risk, an indicator that is inversely proportional to the effectiveness of hard skills (major).

4 Methodology

To assess the criticality of the module compensation mode, its complex operating principle is detailed in Table 3 and based on the logical conditions outlined below.

This mode is applied to 24 modules over the course of the degree program, spanning 3 years, with 8 modules per year and 4 modules per semester.

Number of modules marks < 10/20	Situation	Deficit	Sum of Excess Points is greater than:	Number of Compensations
1	Possible	1 module	10 minus the module mark	1
2	Possible	2 modules	20 minus the sum of the marks of the two modules	2
2	Possible	2 modules	10 minus the sum of the marks of the two modules	1
3	Possible	3 modules	30 minus the sum of the marks of the three modules	3
3	Possible	2 modules	20 minus the sum of the marks of the two modules	2
3	Possible	1 module	Module deficit	1
4	Impossible	4 modules	0	0

Table 3. Mode of the module's compensation

Examining this table reveals the following logical conditions:

- Compensation cannot be applied to more than three modules. Therefore, if the semester average is less than 10/20, no compensations will be recorded
- If a single module has a mark below 10/20 and the sum of the excess points from the validated module(s) is greater than or equal to the deficit (10 minus the module's mark), then one compensation will be recorded
- If two modules have marks below 10/20 and the sum of the excess points from the validated module(s) is greater than or equal to:
 - The combined deficit of the two modules (20 minus the sum of the marks of the two modules), then two compensations will be recorded
 - The deficit of only one module (10 minus the module's mark), then one compensation will be recorded
- If three modules have marks below 10/20 and the sum of the excess points from the validated module(s) is greater than or equal to:
 - The combined deficit of the three modules (30 minus the sum of the marks of the three modules), then three compensations will be recorded

- The combined deficit of two modules (20 minus the sum of the marks of the two modules), then two compensations will be recorded
- The deficit of a single module, then one compensation will be recorded

Upon examining this logical mechanism, it becomes evident that the principle of compensation is complex. Moreover, it is apparent that a higher number of excess points (beyond the minimum average of 10/20) increases the likelihood that a student can validate missed modules and, consequently, address skills they initially lacked. This constitutes a critical flaw in the performance of the LMD education system.

5 Findings and research outcomes

5.1 Analysis and interpretation of the compensation mechanism

It is only possible to know whether a student could probably end up in a catch-up session until after their first marks have been obtained. In other words, the more marks a student receives below the average ($< 10/20$), the higher their probability of needing to compensate for modules

Additionally, the probability of compensation also depends on the number of times a student accesses the catch-up sessions. Specifically, the probability increases with the number of modules in which the score is less than 10/20.

To more accurately approximate the compensation frequency indicator, the second factor: *the frequency of access to catch-up sessions should be considered*. The principle is straightforward: if a student frequently retakes their module exams, they may continue to do so in subsequent semesters. Therefore, the probability of needing compensation would also increase with the frequency of access to catch-up sessions. This compensation risk is determined by the key performance indicators (KPIs) that have been developed.

5.2 Description of indicators (KPIs)

5.2.1 Indicator 1 : Compensation frequency (KPI 1) .

Since the compensation indicator is expressed as continuous variables, a derived indicator was introduced. This indicator, represented by discrete variables, is more representative and indicates the frequency of compensation through five proportional categories listed in Table 4. This derived indicator helps identify students who may graduate with insufficient skills in their major due to an excessive compensation rate.

Number of Modules to Compensate	Mention
0	No compensation
≤ 3	Very low
≤ 6	Medium
≤ 12	High
≤ 24	Very high

Table 4. Mentions of Compensation Frequency

The interpretation of Table 4 is given according to the following logic:

- If no modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is zero (no compensation)
- If fewer than 3 modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is very low
- If fewer than 6 modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is low
- If fewer than 9 modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is medium
- If fewer than 12 modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is high
- If fewer than 24 modules are compensated, the compensation frequency is very high

It is to highlight that the more the student advances in the semesters, the more reliable and relevant the indicator becomes.

5.2.2 Indicator 2: Compensation alert (KPI 2) .

Indicated by mentions at five different criticality levels, the alert for catch-up sessions is determined by the sum of module units (subjects) in a session compared to the overall sum of module units.

For example, the Mineral Chemistry Module II in Semester 3 (second year) includes crystal chemistry, solution chemistry, and descriptive chemistry, which totals 3 subjects or 3 units. Therefore, we refer to a sum, not a number, because each unit is represented by the number 1, with a possible limit of 4 units per module.

The different possible cases are described according to the following logic:

- If at least 3/4 of the module units are to be caught up, then the compensation would be very likely.
- If half of the module units are to be caught up, then the compensation would be likely.
- If 1/4 of the module units are to be caught, then the compensation would be unlikely.
- If less than 1/4 of the module units are to be caught, then the compensation would be very unlikely.

- If no module unit is to be caught, then there would be no probable alert (no alert).

Applying this reasoning to the example above, if a student scores greater than or equal to 10 out of 20 in two out of three units, the ratio would be 2/3.

5.3 Measuring the compensation risk probability

5.3.1 Method of calculating KPIs .

The method of calculating KPIs is given by Equation 1 and Equation 2 as follows, where M is the number of modules and U the number of module units:

$$\text{KPI 1} = 1 - \frac{M_{\text{Compensated after catch-up session}}}{M_{\text{Total in catch-up session}}} \quad (1)$$

Equation 1: Compensation frequency equation

$$\text{KPI 2} = 1 - \frac{U_{\text{(catch-up session)}}}{U_{\text{(Total in normal session)}}} \quad (2)$$

Equation 2: Compensation alert equation

KPI 1 is defined using five thresholds: 0, 3, 9, 12, and 24. These thresholds correspond to proportions of 0, 1/8, 3/8, 1/2, and 1, respectively, which represent the possible compensations across all 24 modules in a licensing cycle. These can be expressed as proportions of 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1. The KPI equations are calculated as a ratio subtracted from 1 to ensure its value remains between 0 and 1.

KPI 2 is determined based on one of four levels of performance, depending on whether the student is required to pass four modules in a semester. Additionally, the relevance of this indicator increases with the number of module exams taken.

5.3.2 The equation measuring the compensation risk probability .

These two indicators, KPI 1 and KPI 2, identified above as the most relevant for assessing the risk of compensation in the LMD system, are incorporated respectively into Equation 3 and Equation 4, each with a different level of precision.

$$P_1 = \prod_{i=1}^2 \text{KPI}_i ; P_1 \in [0, 1] \quad (3)$$

Equation 3: Compensation alert equation - General estimation

$$P_2 = \sum_{i=1}^2 C_i \cdot KPI_i ; P_2 \in [0, 1] \quad (4)$$

Equation 4: Compensation alert equation - Refined estimation

These two equations are interpreted as follows:

- **The probability of compensation risk P1 given by (3) is a product KPI 1 × KPI 2:**

In this case, KPI 1 is considered to be a factor of KPI 2 and vice versa.

- **The probability of compensation risk P2 given by (4) is a linear form (a × KPI 1 + b × KPI 2):**

The effectiveness of Equation 4 depends on the coefficients assigned to each indicator, reflecting their relative importance.

The bounds of this interval represent zero compensation frequency and no probability of catch-up at the lower bound 0. Conversely, the upper bound 1 indicates a very high risk of compensation, and not an inevitable compensation, as there is no scenario where all module units would require compensation.

Thus, based on P1 and P2, as the values of the two KPIs increase, so does the probability of compensation risk. This means that as both the frequency of compensation and the catch-up alert indicator rise, the compensation risk also increases.

5.3.3 The weighting of the coefficients in equation 2 .

In the case of this study, and depending on the mechanism of the LMD system on which it was carried out, the following weightings were observed, specified in Table 5:

KPI	Weight	Coefficient
Compensation frequency (KPI 1)	75%	C1
Compensation alert (KPI 2)	25%	C2

Table 5. Weighting of indicators in equation 2

The weights of these two indicators prioritize KPI 1. These proportions were established Based on CSEFRS (2018), which clearly indicate that students are massively compensating for modules, at least one module among the four modules per semester (2 major and 2 soft skills), which should exceed 75%.

Additionally, KPI 1 accounts for the compensation of an entire module, whereas KPI 2 pertains only to compensation at the unit level. A module typically consists of 2 to 4 units.

These weights may be modified or adjusted as necessary, depending on the compensation method and their relative significance within any HEIs operating under the LMD system that employ these equations.

5.3.4 Interpretation scale of P1 and P2 .

To establish an adapted scale allowing the values P1 and P2 to be read, the mentions of KPI 1 and those of KPI 2, in Table 6, were crossed.

KPI 1 mention	Associated value	KPI 2 mention	Associated value
no comp	0	Very likely catch-up session	1
very low	0.25	Likely catch-up session	0.75
low	0.5	Catch-up session unlikely	0.5
medium	0.75	Catch-up session very unlikely	0.25
high	0.9	No alert	0
very high	1	No alert	0

Table 6. KPIs mentions and associated values

Based on the fundamental principle of counting in combinatorics, 6 possibilities for the KPI 1 combined to 5 possibilities for the KPI 2 gives 30 scenarios: $6 \times 5 = 30$, which are the different possible scenarios, as shown in Table 7.

KPI 1	KPI 2	Value KPI 1	Value KPI 2	P1 (Equation 1)	P2 (Equation 2)
no comp	Very likely	0	1	0.00	0.25
no comp	Likely	0	0.75	0.00	0.19
no comp	Unlikely	0	0.5	0.00	0.13
no comp	Very unlikely	0	0.25	0.00	0.06
no comp	No alert	0	0	0.00	0.00
very low	Very likely	0.5	1	0.50	0.63
very low	Likely	0.5	0.75	0.38	0.56
very low	Unlikely	0.25	0.5	0.13	0.31
very low	Very unlikely	0.25	0.25	0.06	0.25
very low	No alert	0.25	0	0.00	0.19
low	Very likely	0.25	1	0.25	0.44
low	Likely	0.5	0.75	0.38	0.56
low	Unlikely	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.50
low	Very unlikely	0.5	0.25	0.13	0.44
low	No alert	0.5	0	0.00	0.38
medium	Very likely	0.75	1	0.75	0.81
medium	Likely	0.75	0.75	0.56	0.75
medium	Unlikely	0.75	0.5	0.38	0.69
medium	Very unlikely	0.75	0.25	0.19	0.63
medium	No alert	0.75	0	0.00	0.56
high	Very likely	0.9	1	0.90	0.93
high	Likely	0.9	0.75	0.68	0.86
high	Unlikely	0.9	0.5	0.45	0.80
high	Very unlikely	0.9	0.25	0.23	0.74
high	No alert	0.9	0	0.00	0.68
very high	Very likely	1	1	1.00	1.00
very high	Likely	1	0.75	0.75	0.94
very high	Unlikely	1	0.5	0.50	0.88
very high	Very unlikely	1	0.25	0.25	0.81
very high	No alert	1	0	0.00	0.75

Table 7. Cross-reference between mentions of KPIs

According to the calculated values of P1 and P2 presented in Table 7, the scale derived from the linear form is more precise than that from the product form. Specifically, Equation 4 (P2) exhibits smaller probabilities for unlikely or very improbable cases, and larger probabilities for probable or very probable cases, at bounds 0 and 1, respectively. In contrast, Equation 3 (P1) yields a value of 0 as these bounds are approached.

6 Algorithms, listings and codes for KPI 1 and KPI 2

It is evident that a study focused on performance equations, particularly the calculation of KPIs in educational sciences, becomes even more effective when complemented by digital solutions through educational technologies. Indeed, this section presents algorithms, spreadsheet codes and listings, that clearly explains the logic of equations and KPIs without complex technical details. They are simple, basic, and easy to implement in a spreadsheet, requiring no specific mathematical skills to understand.

Furthermore, these codes, listings, and algorithms are also provided for developers with the perspective of advancing this work further by programming its equations into more advanced information systems.

6.1 Conditional logical process for KPI 1

Algorithm 1 shows the logic of the module compensation principle, represented by KPI 1, with the mentions previously cited in Table 4.

Algorithm 1 Compensation Frequency Logic

```
if SUM of NB compensated modules = 0 then  
    "no comp."  
else if SUM of NB compensated modules < 3 then  
    "very low"  
else if SUM of NB compensated modules < 6 then  
    "low"  
else if SUM of NB compensated modules < 9 then  
    "medium"  
else if SUM of NB compensated modules < 12 then  
    "high"  
else if SUM of NB compensated modules < 24 then  
    "very high"  
end if
```

Based on the 24 modules during the license cycle (bachelor), KPI 1 can be expressed in a spreadsheet by a simple combination of a logical test function as shown in Listing 1.1, where cell A1 represents the sum of the number of compensated modules.

Listing 1.1. Spreadsheet functions of Compensation Frequency

```
=IF(SUM(A1)=0, "no comp.",  
    IF(SUM(A1)<3, "very low",  
    IF(SUM(A1)<6, "low",  
    IF(SUM(A1)<9, "medium",  
    IF(SUM(A1)<12, "high",  
    IF(SUM(A1)<24, "very high",  
    ""))))))
```

6.2 Conditional logical process for KPI 2

KPI 2, which represents the alerts for catch-up session, detailed in Indicator 2, subsection 5.2.2, is written in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Compensation alert

```
if SUM(NB units in catch-up session) / SUM(NB units in normal session) <  
25 then  
    "very likely catch-up session"  
else if SUM(NB units in catch-up session) / SUM(NB units in normal session)  
< 50 then  
    "likely catch-up session"  
else if SUM(NB units in catch-up session) / SUM(NB units in normal session)  
< 75 then  
    "catch-up session unlikely"  
else if SUM(NB units in catch-up session) / SUM(NB units in normal session)  
< 100 then  
    "catch-up session very unlikely"  
else if SUM(NB units in catch-up session) / SUM(NB units in normal session)  
= 100 then  
    "no alert"  
end if
```

The thresholds 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 and 1 correspond to rates chosen according to the number of modules per semester which is four, where 25% of the 4 modules would represent 1 module in catch-up session and so on.

In a spreadsheet, this indicator can be expressed by a combination of a logical test functions as shown in Listing 1.2, Where cells A1 and B1 represent respectively the sum of the number of compensated modules and the sum of the number of units in normal session.

Listing 1.2. Spreadsheet functions of compensation alert

```
=IF(A1/B1<=0.25, "very likely catch-up session",  
    IF(A1/B1<=0.50, "likely catch-up session",  
    IF(A1/B1<=0.75, "catch-up session unlikely",  
    IF(A1/B1<1, "catch-up session very unlikely",  
    IF(A1/B1=1, "no alert",  
    ""))))))
```

7 Discussion

The equations developed, specifically the KPIs, should first be monitored by professors, as they are the primary stakeholders. Additionally, faculty administrators should track these KPIs to measure the extent of the decline in the quality of university education. This will enable them to rigorously and strictly regulate the completion of majors (hard skills) with complementary modules (soft skills).

Furthermore, the compensation risk equations developed are not limited to the two indicators currently included. Additional relevant KPIs could be incorporated to enhance the accuracy of assessing the imminence of risk. Understanding the degree of this risk could help revise the compensation policies adopted by certain HEIs, especially when the probability is high among students who have successfully completed their university courses.

Additionally, the provided algorithms, codes, and listings can automate the calculation of this probability in spreadsheets or through more advanced software programs. With the integration of a dashboard, this would make the calculation of compensation risk probability more autonomous and accessible.

8 Conclusion

The use of compensation risk probability, as represented by the two equations P1 and P2, depends on the specific configuration of the LMD system being studied. While the product form (P1) is more general and applicable to various LMD configurations, the linear form (P2) may require adjustments to its parameters, particularly the weighting coefficients C1 and C2, based on how soft skills modules impact the average results by compensating the majors.

Ultimately, the equations designed to measure compensation risk probability aim to address educational issues by evaluating the effectiveness of the LMD system in managing compensation risk. This work characterizes such risks as critical flaws that may be observed in certain (HEIs) adopting this system. The indicators included in these equations highlight that the way modules are compensated could potentially contribute to post-university failure, especially in scientific and technical fields.

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